

BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM WITH NONLINEAR GLUING CONDITION FOR A LOADED WAVE-DIFFUSION EQUATION INVOLVES FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVE

O.Kh. Abdullaev, Kh.A. Shokosimova

¹Alfraganus University. Tashkent. Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15291896>

Abstract. This work devoted to the unique solvability of boundary value problem with nonlinear gluing condition for the loaded parabolic-hyperbolic equation involving the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative have been investigated.

Key words: Loaded equation, wave-diffusion equation, Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative, existence and uniqueness of solution, nonlinear gluing condition, nonlinear integral equations.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu ishda Rimann-Liuvill kasr tartibli hosilasi ishtirokidagi yuklangan parabolik-giperbolik tenglama uchun chiziqsiz ulash shartli chegaraviy masalaning bir qiymatli yechilishi isbotlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: yuklangan tenglama, kasr tartibli hosila, diffuziya-to'ldin tenglamasi, usluksiz ulash shart, yechim mavjudligi va yagonaligi, chiziqsiz integral tenglama.

Аннотация. В работе доказано однозначная разрешимость краевой задачи с нелинейной условию склейки для нагруженного парабола-гиперболического уравнения с дробной производной Римана-Лиувилля.

Ключевые слова: нагруженное уравнение, диффузионно-волновое уравнение, условие нелинейной склейки, существование и единственность решения, нелинейное интегральное уравнение.

This work deals the existence and uniqueness of solution of the local problem with nonlinear gluing condition for loaded mixed type equation involving the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative.

Problem formulation.

We consider the equation:

$$0 = \begin{cases} u_{xx} - D_{oy}^\alpha u + y^{\alpha-1} p(x, y, u(x, 0)), & \text{at } y > 0 \\ u_{xx} - u_{yy} + q(x, y, u(x, 0)), & \text{at } y < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with the Riemann-Liouville operator [1],

$$D_{oy}^\alpha u = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dy} \int_0^y (y-t)^{-\alpha} u(x, t) dt, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1. \quad (2)$$

Let us, Ω is domain, bounded with segments: $A_1A_2 = \{(x, y) : x = 1, 0 < y < h\}$,

$B_1B_2 = \{(x, y) : x = 0, 0 < y < h\}$, $B_2A_2 = \{(x, y) : y = h, 0 < x < 1\}$ at the $y > 0$,

and characteristics : $A_1C : x - y = 1$; $B_1C : x + y = 0$ of the equation (1) at $y < 0$, where

$$A_1(1;0), A_2(1;h), B_1(0;0), B_2(0;h), C\left(\frac{1}{2}; -\frac{1}{2}\right).$$

We enter designations: $\Omega^+ = \Omega \cap (y > 0)$, $\Omega^- = \Omega \cap (y < 0)$, $I_1 = \left\{x : 0 < x < \frac{1}{2}\right\}$,

$$I_2 = \{y : 0 < y < h\}.$$

In the domain of Ω the following problem is investigated.

Problem I. To find a solution $u(x, y)$ of the equation (1) from the following class of functions:

$$W = \left\{u : D_{0y}^{\alpha-1}u(x, y) \in C(\bar{\Omega}^+), u(x, y) \in C(\bar{\Omega}^-) \cap C^2(\Omega^-), y^{1-\alpha}u(x, y) \in C^1(\bar{\Omega}^+)$$

$$y^{1-\alpha}u_{xx} \in C(\Omega^+), D_{oy}^\alpha u \in C(\Omega^+ \cup I)\right\} \text{ satisfies boundary conditions:}$$

$$u_x(0, y) = \varphi_1(y), 0 \leq y \leq h, \quad u_x(1, y) = \varphi_2(y), 0 \leq y \leq h, \quad (5)$$

$$u(x, -x) = \psi(x), \quad x \in \bar{I}_1, \quad (6)$$

and gluing conditions:

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} y^{1-\alpha}u(x, y) = u(x, -0), \quad (7)$$

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} y^{1-\alpha} \left(y^{1-\alpha}u(x, y) \right)_y = r(x, u_y(x, -0)), \quad (x, 0) \in A_1B_1 \quad (8)$$

where $\varphi_i(y)$ ($i=1,2$), $\psi(x)$, $r(x, z)$ are given functions.

Method of investigation.

In order to complete prove well-posedness (correctness) of the formulated problem, required to prove uniqueness and existence of solution of the posed problem.

Existence and uniqueness of solution we will prove by the methods of successive approximations and Integral equations.

REFERENCES

1. B.J.Kadirkulov, Boundary problems for mixed parabolic-hyperbolic equations with two lines of changing type and fractional derivative, EJDE, 57(2014),1-7.
2. A.M.Nakhushev, The loaded equations and their applications.,Moscow, Nauka,2012 (in Russian)
3. K.B.Sabitov, Initial-boundaryproblem for parabolic-hyperbolic equation with loaded summands, Russian Math. Iz. VUZ 59(2015), no. 6,23-33. DOI: 10.3103/S1066360X15060055
4. O.Kh.Abdullaev, A non-local problem for a loaded mixed-type equation with a integral operators, J.Samara State Tech.Univ.Phys.and Math. Sci.,20(2016), no.2,220-240 (in Russian).